

DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND KNOWLEDGE LEVEL INFLUENCED IMPLEMENTATION OF POSTPARTUM GYMNASTIC IN NORMAL POSTPARTUM MOTHER

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. Postpartum gymnastic are motion exercise that are performed as soon as possible after giving birth, so that the muscles that experience stretching during pregnancy and childbirth can return to normal conditions as before. This study aimed to analyzed demographic factors and knowledge level with the implementation of postpartum gymnastic in normal postpartum mother.

Method. This research design used cross sectional method. The sampling method used purposive sampling with criteria: normal postpartum mother with age 18-45 years old. Samples were taken in Sidokumpul Bungah Gresik village with 30 respondents for two months from population of 32 respondents. The independent variables were demographic factors (information resource, employment, education level, and parity) and knowledge level. The dependent variable was the implementation of postpartum gymnastic. The instruments used were questionnaires and implementation of postpartum gymnastic check list. The research data were analyzed using Regression Linier.

Result & Analysis. The results of the Linear Regression statistical test showed that demographic factors (sources of information, employment, and education) and the level of knowledge affect the implementation of postpartum gymnastic in normal postpartum mothers. The correlation number for the level of knowledge is the greatest ($r = 0.785$) so that it has the strongest level of influence of the relationship with the implementation of postpartum gymnastic. The relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, so it means that the level of knowledge is increased then the implementation of postpartum gymnastic will increase.

Discussion. This research is expected to be able to make information on nurse intervention increase patient knowledge in the implementation of postpartum gymnastic so as to help accelerate recovery of postpartum mothers.

Keywords: aromatherapy lemon, nausea vomiting, pregnant women

INTRODUCTION

The postpartum period is the period after childbirth and the birth of the baby, the placenta, and the membranes needed to restore the uterine organs, such as before pregnancy, with a time of approximately 6 weeks (Astri, 2014). The puerperium period is the time used to

supervise post-partum mothers to avoid death caused by bleeding. Postpartum maternal mortality usually occurs within 6 to 8 hours post-partum. This is caused by infection, bleeding and post-partum eclampsia (Manuaba, 2010). To reduce the morbidity rate in the post-partum period, namely by doing postpartum exercise which aims to stimulate the

uterine muscles to function optimally so that post-partum hemorrhage is expected not to occur (Maryunani and Sukaryati, 2011). The results of a preliminary study in Sidokumpul Bungah Village on April 13, 2020, in the last 3 months there were 32 patients giving birth. Based on the results of interviews from 32 post-partum mothers, it was found that 3 post-partum mothers did not know and did postpartum exercises while 29 post-partum mothers had not yet been interviewed so the results are not yet known.

According to WHO (2015) Over a period of 25 years, 1990 to 2015, it is estimated that 10.7 million women have died due to childbirth. In 2015, 303,000 maternal deaths occurred worldwide. It is estimated that 25-50% of deaths in poor countries are caused by bleeding, eclampsia and infection. Based on the Indonesian Ministry of Health in 2015-2017, the maternal mortality rate decreased from 2015 to 4,999 cases, in 2016 to 4,1912 cases and in 2017 it decreased to 1717 cases. In 2015, the maternal mortality rate in East Java Province decreased to 89.6 per 100,000 live births and increased again in 2016 the maternal mortality rate in East Java Province reached 91.00 per 100,000 live births (Dinas Kesehatan Provinsi Jawa Timur, 2012). In Gresik Regency, the maternal mortality rate in 2017 was 91.72 per 100,000 live births and then increased in 2018 to 96.64 per 100,000 live births. The maternal mortality rate in Gresik Regency in 2018 was dominated by three main causes, namely eclampsia, bleeding and heart disease (Kementrian Kesehatan RI, 2015).

Postpartum gymnastics is rarely done because postpartum mothers are afraid to do a lot of movement, are afraid of loose stitches, are still sick with perineal wounds and there is a belief that has been developed and believed by the community, namely if it is not yet 40 days after giving birth, the mother is not allowed to do activities (Ambarwati and

Diah, 2010). The impacts that occur if you do not do puerperal exercise include varicose veins, venous thrombosis due to venous obstruction by blood clots that are not smooth due to the mother's limiting movement during the puerperium, infection due to improper uterine involution so that the remaining blood cannot be removed, and abnormal bleeding. By doing puerperal exercise, it can stimulate uterine contractions better so as to avoid the risk of bleeding (Yuanita and Fatmawati, 2019).

The puerperium is the time needed to restore the reproductive organs after delivery and return to their pre-pregnancy condition. The process of restoring health during childbirth is very important for mothers after giving birth. During pregnancy and childbirth, the ligaments and diaphragm of the pelvis and fascia are stretched. It is not uncommon for the rotundum ligament to become loose which causes the uterus to fall backwards. It is not uncommon for women to complain that their "uterus has decreased" after childbirth because the ligaments, fascia, and tissue supporting the genitalia become slightly loose. To restore the tissues supporting the genitalia, as well as the muscles of the abdominal wall and pelvic floor, it is recommended to do certain exercises. Another advantage of these exercises is that they can prevent blood static which can cause thrombosis during the puerperium (Halimah and Anshar, 2018). Postpartum exercise is a movement exercise that is carried out as soon as possible after giving birth, so that the muscles that are stretched during pregnancy and childbirth can return to their normal state (Maryunani and Sukaryati, 2011). Besides speeding up recovery, postpartum exercise can also prevent postpartum bleeding. Knowledge or cognitive is a very important domain for the formation of one's actions and from experience it turns out that behavior is based on knowledge (Notoadmodjo, 2007).

METHOD AND ANALYSIS

This research design was a correlation study using cross sectional method. Each research subject was observed only once and measurements were made of the character or subject variables at the time of examination (Notoatmojo, 2012).

Data collection used questionnaires sheet of demographic and level of knowledge, also a checklist sheet for the implementation of postpartum exercise on March 27– 21 May 2020. The population in this study were 30 postpartum mothers in Sidokumpul Village, Bungah District, Gresik Regency. The sample size was determined using purposive sampling with the criteria: postpartum normal and age between 18-45 years old. The independent variables in this study were demographic factors (information sources, employment, education level, parity) and the level of knowledge of postpartum mothers. The dependent variable in this study was the implementation of postpartum gymnastic. In this study, the process of data collection was obtained through:

1. Get permission from the University of Gresik.
2. Obtaining a permit from the Village of Sidokumpul Bungah.
3. Looking for data on postpartum mothers by asking for data from village midwives who work at the ponkesdes.
4. Respondents are given an explanation of the benefits and objectives of the study to obtain respondents' approval.
5. Respondents were given an informed consent sheet to sign their consent to become respondents.
6. Provide a questionnaire on demographics and level of knowledge that is filled in by the respondent, while for the implementation of postpartum exercise using a check list

that is directly observed by the researcher.

7. The data obtained will be collected and then analyzed.

RESULT

1. Demographic Factors in The Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastic

Table 1. Distribution of Demographic Factors for Postpartum Exercise in Normal Postpartum Mothers in Sidokumpul Bungah Gresik Village on 27 March - 21 May 2020.

Demographic Factors	Criteria	Freq.	Sig. 2 tailed	r
Sources of Information	No Information	50 %	0,000	0,682
	Friends/Neighbour	0 %		
	Counseling	0 %		
	Mass Media	50 %		
	Housewife	63,3 %		
Employment	Entrepreneur	6,7 %	0,000	0,733
	Government	23,3 %		
	Employees	6,7 %		
	Health Workers	6,7 %		
Level of Education	Junior High School	33,3 %	0,000	0,704
	Senior High School	36,7 %		
	Bachelor	23,3 %		
	Bachelor	23,3 %		

	Master Degree	6,7 %		
Parity	Primipara	43,3 %	0,161	-0,188
	Multipara	56,7 %		

The results of the Linear Regression statistical test showed that demographic factors (sources of information, employment, and education) affect the implementation of postpartum exercise in normal post-partum mothers and these demographic factors have a positive correlation.

2. Relationship Knowledge Level and Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastic

Table 2. Cross Tabulation of Knowledge Levels with the Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastics for Normal Postpartum Mothers in Sidokumpul Bungah Village, Gresik on March 27 - May 21, 2020.

Knowledge Level	Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastic			
	Less	Enough	Good	Total
Less	1	1	0	2
Enough	3	3	0	6
Good	0	8	14	22
Total	4	12	14	30

Regresi Linier Sig. (2-tailed) = 0,006
r = 0,785

Table 2 shows that the significance value is 0.006, which means that there is a significant relationship between the knowledge level variable and the implementation of postpartum exercise. The coefficient value of 0.785 indicates a strong and positive correlation between

the variable level of knowledge and the implementation of postpartum exercise, so that the relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, meaning that the level of knowledge is increased, the implementation of postpartum exercise will be better.

Table 2 shows the results of the research of 30 respondents, mostly 22 respondents (73%), the level of knowledge of postpartum mothers was good, 6 respondents (20%) had sufficient knowledge of postpartum mothers, and 2 respondents (7%) had less knowledge of postpartum mothers. Knowledge according to Reber (Reber and Emily, 2010) in its collective meaning, Knowledge is a collection of information that is owned by a person or group, or a certain culture. Whereas in general knowledge is the mental components that result from any process, whether born from innate or achieved through experience.

DISCUSSION

1. Demographic Factors in The Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastic

According to Lawrence Green's theory in Notoatmodjo (Notoadmodjo, 2007) classifies several factors that cause an action or behavior, namely predisposing factors which are the factors that form the basis of a person's motivation or intention to do something. Driving factors include knowledge, attitudes, beliefs, values and perceptions, traditions, and other elements contained in individuals and communities related to health. The results showed that half of the respondents know about postpartum exercise from the mass media and who carry out postnatal exercise well.

Other factors that influence implementation are enabling factors, which are factors that enable or facilitate behavior or action. Enabling factors include health facilities and infrastructure or facilities or facilities. The results of the interviews with the respondents did not yet have a special program for postpartum mothers from the Ponkesdes side.

Reinforcing factors are factors that encourage or strengthen a person's behavior due to the attitudes of husbands, parents, community leaders or health workers. The results showed that on average the respondents did not do puerperal exercise in the afternoon and it was only done in the morning, because the postpartum mother felt tired after doing activities all day.

Another demographic factor is the factor of education, the higher a person's education, it is hoped that the knowledge and skills will be better. The results showed that most of the postpartum mothers who knew the postpartum gymnastics with the last S1 education were 6 people (40%).

The results showed that most of the postpartum mothers who knew postpartum gymnastics worked as teachers as many as 6 people (40%). This can be explained that mothers who have jobs outside the home are quicker and easier to get information from outside. Besides that, the most research result of the source of information is the mass media. Mass media referred to as online mass media, such as: articles / online tabloids and social media that provide health information sharing.

The results of the research on parity demographic factors also showed insignificant results, because both the multiparous and the primiparous did postpartum exercise. The results of this study are almost the same as research conducted by Indah (Indah, 2015) regarding the level of knowledge of postpartum mothers about postpartum exercise at Assalam Gemolong Hospital

with the results that the level of knowledge of postpartum mothers is still sufficient, due to several driving factors, namely education and work, while the inhibiting factors are age, parity, information and environment.

2. Relationship Knowledge Level and Implementation of Postpartum Gymnastic

Many factors affect a person's knowledge according to Bakar et.al (Bakar *et al.*, 2017), including: Age, education, occupation, sources of information and experience. Based on the results of the study, most of the postpartum mothers who knew postpartum exercise aged 26-35 years were 13 people (87%). There are factors that affect the level of knowledge of postpartum mothers, namely age which is closely related to one's knowledge, because the older the child has, the more knowledge will be obtained. Knowledge or cognitive is a very important domain for the formation of one's actions and from experience it turns out that behavior is based on knowledge (Notoadmodjo, 2007).

The results showed that there were still postpartum women who did postpartum exercise with a sufficient category because many had not done the third movement of the toe in a circular motion from outside to inside and postpartum mothers were still doing postpartum exercise only in the morning, not doing it in the afternoon. The results showed 30 respondents, mostly postpartum mothers, did the postpartum exercise in the good category as many as 14 people (47%), 12 people (40%) in enough category, and 4 people (13%) in less category.

In this study, the researchers did not observe the postpartum exercise as a whole, but only the implementation of the 7th day exercises. The postpartum exercise on day 7 is movement of the toes such as clawing and stretching, followed by

regular toe movements like a circle. from the outside to the inside, then move your left and right foot up and down like a saw. Perform this movement for half a minute each with 10-15 movements in the morning and evening (Maryunani and Sukaryati, 2011).

CONCLUSION

Demographic factors (sources of information, employment, and education) and the level of knowledge affect the implementation of postpartum exercise in normal postpartum mothers. The correlation number for the level of knowledge is the greatest so that it has the strongest level of influence with the implementation of postpartum exercise. The relationship between the two variables is unidirectional, so that if the level of knowledge is increased, the implementation of postpartum exercise will increase.

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